

The Effect of Surface-Active Substances on Positive Maximum of Tl (I)

Sudarshan Lal and S. N. Srivastava

Effects of external high resistance, varying concentrations of supporting electrolyte and that of the depolarizer have been studied for thallium maximum. Relative efficacies of anionic, cationic, nonionic and inorganic anions for the suppression of thallium maximum have been compared.

Originally, Heyrovsky and Dillinger¹ reported that thalious sulphate exhibited a prominent adsorption maximum on a C-V curve. Later on, Heyrovsky² ascertained that acid dyes *viz.*, sodium salt of methyl red and negative colloids *e.g.*, barium soap solution could suppress the positive Tl (I) maximum conveniently. Suppressive effect of OH⁻ and SO₄²⁻ ions was shown to be more than that of NO₃⁻ ions³. Camphor, triton X-100 and gelatin did not affect⁴ C-V curves of Tl (I) and this fact was utilised in its polarographic estimation by Shetty and co-workers⁵. Fujinaga and Izutzuk⁴ reported that triton X-100 and camphor did not affect the height of Tl (I). Gochshtein⁶ ascribed the depression of maximum of Tl (I) by PO₄³⁻ or Al⁺⁺⁺ to the electrocapillary action of Tl (I). Maximum⁷ of thallium in 0.1M KCl was not suppressed by 10⁻⁵M iodide ions.

Thus, from the general survey of literature, it is evident that no systematic work with charge type of surfactants on Tl (I) maximum is available. Therefore, the present study has been undertaken with two different approaches. On one hand, the effects of different surface-active substances (SAS), their determination of maximum suppression point (MSP) and half suppression (HS) have been attempted while on the other hand effects of inorganic anions, resistance, varying amounts of depolarizer and base electrolyte have been examined.

EXPERIMENTAL

TlNO₃ was a G.R. E.Merck product and all solutions were prepared in conductivity water. KNO₃ (B.D.H.) was used as an indifferent electrolyte. For the record of polarograms, a Manual Polarograph (Southern Analytical) in conjunction with a Pye galvanometer (W.G. Pye, England) was employed. The d.m.e. had the characteristics $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 1.85 \text{ mg}^{2/3}\text{sec}^{-1}$. All measurements were made at 25° at a height of 110.7 cm of mercury column.

1. J. Heyrovsky and H. Dillinger, *Collection Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1930, **2**, 626.
2. J. Heyrovsky and J. Kuta, "Principles of Polarography", Academic Press, New York, 1966, p. 434.
3. *ibid.*, p. 438.
4. T. Fujinaga and Izutzuk, *Japan Analyst*, 1961, **10**, 63.
5. P. S. Shetty, P. R. Subbaraman and J. Gupta, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1962, **27**, 429.
6. J. P. Gochshtein, *J. Gen. Chem. Russ.*, 1940, **10**, 1663.
7. I. M. Kolthoff and Y. Okinaka, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 47.

RESULTS

A. *Effect of concentration of depolarizer—Tl(I)*: At lower concentrations of Tl(I) no maximum is produced. However, at the threshold concentration 1.6 mM maximum is obtained, which increases disproportionately with increasing concentration of the depolarizers. A few results are tabulated below:

TABLE 1

Variation of i_{max} for Tl(I) with its concentration

Concentration of Tl(I)	E_{max} V vs. S.C.E.	i_{max} μ a
1.2 mM	No maximum	8.6*
1.6 „	-0.51	13.5
2.0 „	-0.52	19.4
3.2 „	-0.54	57.0
4.0 „	-0.54	66.8

* Shows absence of maximum.

No linear plot is found for maximum current (i_{max}) vs. concentration of Tl(I). This implies that process is no longer diffusion controlled.

At 3.2 mM concentration of Tl(I), a well pronounced maximum is obtained. This serves as a ground solution and all the following studies are performed with this solution.

B. *Influence of KNO_3 , the supporting electrolyte*: The influence of varying amounts of KNO_3 , the base electrolyte is summarised in the Table 2.

TABLE 2

Concentration of KNO_3	E_{max} V vs. S.C.E.	i_{max} μ a	$K\Omega^{-1}cm^{-1} \times 10^5$
0.0 M	-0.65	35.1	—
0.05 M	-0.54	52.2	4.07
0.10 M	-0.54	58.5	8.14
0.20 M	-0.53	59.2	15.60
0.50 M	-0.55	43.1	31.60
1.0 M	-0.55	38.3	61.10
1.5 M	-0.54	32.7	90.30

E_{max} , in presence of the indifferent electrolyte, lies in the vicinity of -0.53 V to -0.55V. With the increasing concentration of the supporting electrolyte, the maximum attains its highest value of 0.2 M concentration of KNO_3 and with further increase in

concentration of KNO_3 , it decreases. A plot of equivalent conductivity vs. i_{max} (Fig. 1) also displays an analogous behaviour. At higher conductivity values, the extent of maxi-

imum is diminished and waves tend to acquire the shape of limiting plateaus. At the optimum conductivity, $K_{opt} = 15.6 \times 10^{-5} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ at which the maximum achieves its highest value, it obeys the empirical relation :

$$K_{opt} = 0.05 C \text{ where } C \text{ is the depolarizer.}$$

C. *Effect of varying heights of mercury column* : Figure 2 shows the changes in the maximum current with decreasing mercury pressure. With decrease in mercury pressure, the height of maximum undergoes a diminution while at lower heights $e = 50.7 \text{ cm}$ and $f = 30.7 \text{ cm}$, the maximum is quenched. The results indicate that at longer droptimes, the maximum of the first kind disappear.

The plots of i_{max} vs. h and i_{max} vs. $h^{\frac{1}{2}}$ were made. The former showed a linear relationship in the range of polarographic droptimes and the latter gave a curve with an inward curvature characteristic of adsorption⁸. This is indicative of adsorption of the electroactive material on the mercury surface.

8. P. Zuman, "Organic Polarographic Analysis", Pergamon Press, New York, 1964, p. 23.

D. *Resistance in series with the cell*: Tl(I) yields a maximum of the first kind at -0.54 V vs. S.C.E. with $i_{max} = 55 \mu a$. When a high precision resistance $11,000 \Omega$ was connected in series with the polarising circuit, E_{max} was shifted to -0.80 V and the peak of the maximum got rounded with $i_{max} = 24 \mu a$. The shift of E_{max} to more negative potential is attributed to the increased ohmic potential drop in the circuit with increasing external resistance. The rising part of C-V curve was a straight line and its slope was approximately equal to $1/R$. Similar results were obtained by Brdicka⁹ who studied C-V curves of the reduction of Hg(I) and Lingane¹⁰ with O₂, Pb(II), Zn(II) and Ni(II). No reference is however, available describing the effect of external resistance (R_e) on thallium maximum.

E. *Effect of different surfactants*: Effect of various charge type of surfactants and inorganic ions were studied on the morphology of C-V curves. The MSP and HS values of the various surfactants and capillary-active ions are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3

Surfactant		HS	MSP
Nonionic	Caffein	$0.5 \times 10^{-5} \%$	$0.5 \times 10^{-4} \%$
	Triton X-100	$0.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{''}$	$1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{''}$
	Gelatin	$4.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{''}$	$2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{''}$
	Superfloc 16	$2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{''}$	$1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{''}$
	Superfloc 20	$1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{''}$	$1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{''}$
Anionic	Acid fuchsine	$1.20 \times 10^{-5} \%$	$5.0 \times 10^{-5} \%$
	Pepsin	$0.50 \times 10^{-4} \text{''}$	$1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{''}$
	XL-anionic	$0.75 \times 10^{-4} \text{''}$	$2.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{''}$
Cationic detergents	Lauryl Pyridinium bromide (LPB)	$0.25 \times 10^{-6} M$	$5 \times 10^{-6} M$
	Tetradecyl Pyridinium bromide (TPB)	$1.25 \times 10^{-6} M$	$5 \times 10^{-6} M$
	Cetyl Pyridinium bromide (CPB)	$2.00 \times 10^{-6} M$	$1 \times 10^{-6} M$
	Cetyl dimethyl benzyl ammonium chloride (CDBAC)	$1.5 \times 10^{-6} M$	$4 \times 10^{-6} M$
Inorganic anions	Sulphate	$3.34 \times 10^{-2} M$	$0.1 M$
	Citrate	$3.34 \times 10^{-2} M$	$0.2 M$
	Ferrocyanide	$2.00 \times 10^{-4} M$	$10^{-3} M$

For nonionic SAS at the MSP, the E_1 of Tl(I) is almost constant ca. -0.45 V though the wave height is slightly decreased. The efficacy of these SAS is graded in the manner:

The positive maximum of Tl(I) is susceptible to elimination in presence of anionic surfactants as demanded by Heyrovsky's generalisation. The efficacies of the anionic SAS employed are

Studies with cationic detergents reveal that even cationic SAS are suitable for the elimination of positive maximum of Tl(I) which directly depends upon the adsorbability of these surfactants in the potential range studied. The behaviour of the cationic detergents

9. R. Brdicka, *Collection Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1936, 8, 419.

10. J. J. Lingane, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 1665.

is peculiar. The efficiency of LPB is the maximum and that of CPB the least. This may be explained on the basis of orientation of the surface-active agents. When mercury is positively charged, the cationic parts are repelled while the anionic bromide ions oriented towards mercury. But with a smaller chain length, the molecule still remains in the immediate vicinity of the electrode. This ensures close pack up and maximum is suppressed. However, with the increased chain length, the molecules of SAS tend to be away from mercury surface, thus comparatively more amount of SAS is required for maximum suppression.

In order to investigate the effect of valency of anions, SO_4^{-2} , $(\text{citrate})^{-3}$ and $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{-4}$ were employed. The optimum concentrations for these anions for HS and MSP were found. The efficacies are in the following order

This contradicts Heyrovsky's¹¹ rule which states that greater is the valency of an anion, greater is its efficiency for the suppression of positive maxima. However, this case is analogous to Kolthoff and Miller's¹² investigation with oxygen maximum.

The authors are thankful to CSIR, New Delhi for granting a Senior Research Fellowship to one of them (S. L.).

Chemical Laboratories,
Agra College,
Agra.

Received April 26, 1968.

11. J. Heyrovsky, "A Polarographic Study of the Electrokinetic Phenomena of Adsorption, Electro-reduction and Overpotential displayed at dropping mercury cathode", *Actualites Scientifiques etc. industrielles*, No. 90, Hermann etc. Cie., Paris, 1964.
12. I. M. Kolthoff and C. S. Miller, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 1013.